

Movement of Cu, Co and Zn through an undisturbed soil column in a constant flow condition

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Abstract : Transport of some heavy metals (Cu, Co and Zn) through soil of four different locations of West Bengal have been studied by a column experiment in a constant flow condition. The solute or ion flow through soil column along with the solvent is complicated by factors like gravitational forces, diffusibility and dispersibility besides adsorption. The flow rate through soil column is controlled by the soil texture. The question of leaching causing downward migration of heavy metal cations enriching the sub-soil zone is a domain of pollution studies. A mobility parameter for ions has been defined and with its help relative rate of migration of the ions was sought to be defined. All the three ions do not possess the same penetration and mobility characteristics. Some further work is called for to increase the scope of this investigation.

Keywords : Adsorption, Cu, Co, Zn, soils.

Introduction

When sewage sludge and industrial effluents are applied to land for disposal or intended beneficial use, heavy metals accumulate in the soil. Because of the concern about the environmental danger that these sludge-borne metals could represent if mobilized, many studies have been undertaken in an attempt to clarify the different factors that contribute to metal solubility, plant uptake and leachability^{1,2}. The influence of dispersion phenomena in modifying the shape of solute front through a soil column was studied by many workers^{3,4}. It is generally accepted that all the relevant parameters which determine solute displacement in soil are still obscure. Making use of computer facilities some illuminating results were obtained.

When a pure solvent flows into a soil column, hydraulic potential constituting both pressure potential and gravitational potential mainly regulates the flow. But movement of solute in the solvent phase was controlled also by some other forces besides hydraulic potential. Adsorption, diffusion, dispersion and/or other forces that hold the solute in the soil matrix are important among them. Under steady state condition the movement of different cations through soil column can be compared in terms of adsorption forces provided other forces are kept constant. Hence the objective of this study is to compare and contrast the relative movement of different cations

through a soil column in a constant flow condition. This study follows the principle of column chromatography.

Results and discussion

When water flows down the soil column the overall flow rate is controlled by the soil texture. It was found from the experiments that the flow rate of solution is least in Bakkhali soil which is richest in clay and silt percentage. The flow rate is highest in Pedong soil. This soil, though relatively rich in organic matter, is poorer in clay and silt content. Gonpur soil though contains high percentage of clay has more of kaolinite than illite. Silt content also is much less than that of Bakkhali soil. Katwa soil contains very modest amounts of both organic matter and clay.

The movement of the dissolved cations on the other hand is influenced by their adsorption in the soil solid phase besides the factors responsible for controlling the solvent mobility. The solute coming out of the soil column are those which are not adsorbed by the soil and remain in the soil solution. The adsorption of the cations on the soil solid phase is a quick reaction, if not instantaneous⁵⁻⁷. Leaching with water removes the cations which are not already bound. The plots of the amount of ions retained in the soil against time show radioactive decay

type of ion attenuation. The relation between this attenuation and time are not exactly linear but probably could be better expressed by the relation $(x_0 - x_t) = ke^{-\alpha t}$, where x_0 is the original amount (meq) of heavy metal cations added and x_t is the amount released at time t . k and α are two constants. The equation can be written in the form $\ln(x_0 - x_t) = \ln k - \alpha t$. Here k approaches the value x_0 at $t = 0$ i.e. when $x = 0$ which is found from the linear plot of $\ln(x_0 - x_t)$ against t . The linearity of the plots (not shown here) justify the basis of the assumption of the equation made. The value of α is constant only for a given ion for a particular soil. This can be treated as mobility parameter of the ion. The values are given in Tables 2-4. The relative values of α gives an estimate of

the ease of penetration and release of Cu, Co and Zn through soils. For Pedong soil α value arrange themselves in the sequence : $\text{Co} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cu}$. This reflects that Cu is retained in Pedong soil maximum which can be attributed to its high organic matter content. Organic matter has been claimed to possess a strong tendency for complexing copper⁸⁻¹⁰. In case of Gonpur soil the decreasing order of α values is $\text{Zn} > \text{Cu} = \text{Co}$. Less retention of Co and Cu is due to its poor organic matter content. The relative order of α values for Katwa soil is $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Zn}$ reflects that Zn is maximum retained by Katwa soil and it is low in both organic matter and clay. For Bakkhali soil the decreasing order of α value is $\text{Co} > \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$, which means Co is adsorbed maximum by this soil followed by Cu and Zn.

Table 1. Soil properties

Properties ^a	Soil locations			
	Pedong	Gonpur	Katwa	Bakkhali
Taxonomic classification	Typic Lithic Udorthents	Typic Ocharaqualfs	Typic Ustifluvents	Typic Haplaquepts
pH (1 : 2)	4.23	6.0	6.5	6.5
CEC [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	9.7	10.0	6.55	15.27
CEC of clay [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	21.78	32.27	20.78	31.64
CEC of humic acid [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	276.0	420.0	403.0	374.0
CaCO ₃ (%)	0.45	1.75	2.10	2.0
Organic matter (%)	6.23	0.74	1.25	1.77
Clay (%)	20.0	32.5	16.0	22.0
Silt (%)	17.0	8.0	3.0	16.0
Fine sand (%)	40.0	26.0	40.0	33.0
Coarse sand (%)	23.0	34.5	41.0	29.0
Mineral phase present	Illite (Tr), Micaceous mineral	Illite (M), Kaolinite	Illite (VS), Kaolinite (S)	Illite (S), Kaolinite (MS)

^aSoil parameters are expressed as average of five replicates. Tr. - Trace; M - Medium; MS - Medium Strong; S - Strong; VS - Very Strong.

Table 2. Cu on different soil

Soil name	Amount of Cu ²⁺ added in the column (meq)	Metal ion-soil ratio (meq/100 g)	Time of flow (min)	Volume of solution collected (ml)	Amount of Cu ²⁺ released (meq)	Amount of Cu ²⁺ retained (meq)	Mobility parameter of Cu ion (α) (meq min ⁻¹)
Pedong	5.0	16.0	30	8.7	0.59	4.41	1.7017×10^{-3}
			60	8.8	0.80	3.61	
			90	8.8	0.43	3.18	
			120	8.6	0.20	2.98	
			150	8.7	0.16	2.82	
			180	8.6	0.12	2.70	
			240	16.2	0.17	2.53	
			360	32.5	0.18	2.35	

Table-2 (contd.)

Gonpur	6.33	16.0	30	5.0	0.04	6.29	1.18×10^{-3}
			60	4.9	0.23	6.06	
			90	4.9	0.33	5.73	
			120	5.1	0.31	5.42	
			150	5.1	0.23	5.19	
			180	5.0	0.19	5.00	
			240	9.8	0.28	4.72	
			360	20.2	0.42	4.30	
Katwa	6.4	16.0	30	7.6	1.6	4.8	1.94×10^{-3}
			60	7.6	1.08	3.72	
			90	7.3	0.49	3.23	
			120	7.4	0.33	2.90	
			150	7.3	0.22	2.68	
			180	7.5	0.12	2.56	
			240	14.2	0.14	2.42	
			360	29.0	0.08	2.34	
Bakkhali	6.33	16.0	30	4.4	0.03	6.3	1.30×10^{-3}
			60	4.4	0.166	6.134	
			90	4.3	0.3	5.834	
			150	8.4	0.608	5.226	
			180	4.2	0.25	4.976	
			240	8.0	0.37	4.606	
			360	16.5	0.40	4.206	

Total amount of Cu^{2+} released in 100.9 ml after 360 min is 2.65 meq in Pedong soil.

Total amount of Cu^{2+} released in 60.0 ml after 360 min is 2.03 meq in Gonpur soil.

Total amount of Cu^{2+} released in 87.9 ml after 360 min is 4.06 meq in Katwa soil.

Total amount of Cu^{2+} released in 50.2 ml after 360 min is 2.124 meq in Bakkhali soil.

Table 3. Co on different soil

Soil name	Amount of Co^{2+} added in the column (meq)	Metal ion-soil ratio (meq/100 g)	Time of flow (min)	Volume of solution collected (ml)	Amount of Co^{2+} released (meq)	Amount of Co^{2+} retained (meq)	Mobility parameter of Co ion (α) (meq min^{-1})
Pedong	5.0	16.0	30	8.8	0.69	4.31	3.1168×10^{-3}
			60	9.0	1.32	2.99	
			90	9.0	0.64	2.35	
			120	8.8	0.38	1.97	
			150	8.8	0.22	1.75	
			180	9.1	0.16	1.59	
			240	16.0	0.17	1.42	
			360	32.4	0.05	1.37	
Gonpur	6.38	16.0	30	5.1	0.013	6.367	1.14×10^{-3}
			60	5.0	0.28	6.087	
			90	5.0	0.41	5.677	
			120	4.8	0.25	5.427	
			150	4.8	0.26	5.167	

Table-3 (contd.)

Katwa	6.39	16.0	180	5.1	0.168	4.999	1.61×10^{-3}
			240	10.0	0.415	4.584	
			360	20.0	0.12	4.464	
			30	7.5	1.39	5.0	
			60	7.6	0.69	4.31	
			90	7.5	0.40	3.91	
			120	7.4	0.33	3.58	
			150	7.4	0.27	3.31	
			180	7.5	0.15	3.16	
Bakkhali	6.38	16.0	240	14.5	0.175	2.985	1.55×10^{-3}
			360	29.2	0.12	2.865	
			30	4.0	0.08	6.3	
			60	3.9	0.125	6.175	
			90	3.9	0.215	5.96	
			120	4.0	0.30	5.66	
			150	4.1	0.32	5.34	
			180	4.0	0.28	5.06	
			240	7.5	0.54	4.52	
			360	14.9	0.62	3.90	

Total amount of Co^{2+} released in 101.9 ml after 360 min is 3.63 meq in Pedong soil.

Total amount of Co^{2+} released in 59.8 ml after 360 min is 1.916 meq in Gonpur soil.

Total amount of Co^{2+} released in 88.6 ml after 360 min is 3.525 meq in Katwa soil.

Total amount of Co^{2+} released in 46.3 ml after 360 min is 2.48 meq in Bakkhali soil.

Table 4. Zn on different soil

Soil name	Amount of Zn^{2+} added in the column (meq)	Metal ion-soil ratio (meq/100 g)	Time of flow (min)	Volume of solution collected (ml)	Amount of Zn^{2+} released (meq)	Amount of Zn^{2+} retained (meq)	Mobility parameter of Zn ion (α) (meq min^{-1})
Pedong	5.0	16.0	30	8.4	0.17	4.83	2.8648×10^{-3}
			60	8.5	0.31	4.52	
			90	8.5	0.45	4.07	
			120	8.5	0.43	3.64	
			150	8.5	0.37	3.27	
			180	8.5	0.36	2.91	
			240	16.0	0.56	2.35	
			360	32.0	0.35	2.00	
Gonpur	6.39	16.0	30	5.1	0.013	6.377	1.42×10^{-3}
			60	5.0	0.126	6.251	
			90	4.9	0.29	5.961	
			120	4.9	0.36	5.601	
			150	5.0	0.308	5.293	
			180	5.0	0.245	5.048	
			240	9.2	0.359	4.689	
			360	20.5	0.62	4.069	

Table-4 (contd.)

Katwa	6.4	16.0	30	7.5	1.26	5.14	1.14×10^{-3}
			60	7.5	0.71	4.43	
			90	7.4	0.38	4.05	
			120	7.3	0.23	3.82	
			150	7.5	0.13	3.69	
			180	7.6	0.093	3.597	
			240	14.6	0.125	3.472	
Bakkhali	6.39	16.0	30	4.4	0.016	6.374	9.79×10^{-4}
			60	4.1	0.1	6.274	
			90	4.1	0.147	6.127	
			120	4.0	0.165	5.962	
			150	4.0	0.168	5.794	
			180	4.0	0.148	5.646	
			240	7.9	0.308	5.338	
		360	16.0	0.72	4.618		

Total amount of Zn^{2+} released in 98.9 ml after 360 min is 3.0 meq in Pedong soil.

Total amount of Zn^{2+} released in 59.6 ml after 360 min is 2.321 meq in Gonpur soil.

Total amount of Zn^{2+} released in 88.9 ml after 360 min is 3.048 meq in Katwa soil.

Total amount of Zn^{2+} released in 48.5 ml after 360 min is 1.772 meq in Bakkhali soil.

Experimental

Sample of soil (0–20 cm surface layer) were collected from four different locations of West Bengal. The soil types and their broad physico-chemical characteristics are out lined in Table 1. These soils differ in composition and developed under four different agro-climatic situations. One soil, Pedong belongs to Dargeeling Himalayan region at an altitude of 1938 m. The second soil was collected from lateritic zone which developed under forest vegetation. The third namely Katwa is an entisol from gangetic alluvium. The last one from Bakkhali belongs to deltaic saline tract.

Soil classification was made as per the map prepared by National Bureau of soil survey and land use planning.

The important allumino silicates in four soils were identified by X-ray diffraction analysis. X-Ray diffraction pattern was recorded in Philips PW-1730 X-ray crystallographic unit provided with a proportional counter, PW-1050/70 Goniometer, PW-1390 electronic using $Cu K_{\alpha}$ radiation with Ni filter. Silt assemble is $1^{\circ} > 0.2 > 1^{\circ}$. The XRD analysis data are given in Table 1.

Adsorption and mobility of heavy metal ions in a constant flow condition was studied by a series of column

experiments. The experiment may be considered to replicate the field condition of natural irrigation and flooding.

A 30 cm pyrex glass column with an uniform inner diameter of 2.21 cm was used. The glass tube is fitted at the bottom with an outlet tube and stop cock. The base of the column was packed with a thin layer of glass, wool. The top was closed with a stopper and inlet tube with the facility of being attached to an aspirator bottle. The junction could be opened and closed by means of a stop cock. The whole set up was set vertically.

The glass tube was closely packed with a fixed quantity of dried soil upto a height of 20 cm. The whole soil mass was first saturated with water.

In separate set of experiments appropriate amounts (roughly 3 times the CEC of the soils) of cobalt, copper and zinc ions in aqueous solutions as metal chlorides were added at the top of the column and allowed to penetrate the soil column. A constant water head of 2 cm was maintained over the soil column. The pressure head above the column thus remained unaltered. A constant flow of water was maintained into the soil column at the top. The solution comes out of it at the bottom at rates controlled by the soil composition and texture. The solution flowing

out of the column was collected at different time intervals and the contents analyzed for Cu, Co and Zn ions.

The amounts of Co, Cu and Zn were measured spectrophotometrically. Co was determined by nitroso-R-salt (Sodium 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy naphthalene-3,6-disulphonate) method^{11,12}. Cu and Zn were determined by Zincon [1-(2-hydroxy-5-sulphophenyl)-3-phenyl-5-(2-carboxy phenyl)formazan] method (Snell and Snell, 1959).

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